

Каньовська Л.В.,
доцент кафедри внутрішньої медицини, клінічної фармакології та професійних хвороб
Буковинський державний медичний університет
Криворука О.Г.,
Криворука О.С.
Студенти 5 курсу
Буковинський державний медичний університет
м. Чернівці, Україна
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18641438>

**АКТУАЛЬНІ ПРИНЦИПИ ЛІКУВАННЯ СЕРЦЕВОЇ НЕДОСТАТНОСТІ ЗІ ЗНИЖЕНОЮ ФРАКЦІЄЮ.
(ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ)**

Kaniowska L.V.,
Associate Professor of the Department of Internal Medicine,
Clinical Pharmacology and Occupational Diseases
Bukovinian State Medical University
Kryvoruka O.G.,
Kryvoruka O.S.
5th year students
Bukovinian State Medical University
Chernivtsi, Ukraine

**ACTUAL PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT OF HEART FAILURE WITH A REDUCED FRACTION
(LITERATURE REVIEW)**

Abstract.

Heart failure with reduced ejection fraction remains one of the leading causes of morbidity, hospitalizations and mortality in the world, despite significant progress in pharmacotherapy and non-drug approaches to treatment. Heart failure with reduced ejection fraction is characterized by a decrease in left ventricular systolic function, which is accompanied by activation of neurohormonal systems, progressive myocardial remodeling and deterioration of hemodynamics. Modern principles of treatment of heart failure with reduced ejection fraction are based on a multilevel pathophysiological approach aimed at suppressing excessive activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone and sympathetic nervous systems, reducing myocardial load, slowing down structural remodeling of the heart and improving the prognosis of patients. The basis of drug therapy is the following angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin II receptor blockers or angiotensin and neprilysin receptor inhibitors, β -blockers, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, and sodium-glucose cotransporter type 2 inhibitors.

Анотація:

Серцева недостатність зі зниженою фракцією викиду залишається однією з провідних причин захворюваності, госпіталізації та смертності у світі, незважаючи на значний прогрес у фармакотерапії та немедикаментозних підходах до лікування. Серцева недостатність зі зниженою фракцією викиду характеризується зниженням систолічної функції лівого шлуночка, що супроводжується активацією нейрогормональних систем, прогресуючим ремоделюванням міокарда та погіршенням гемодинаміки. Сучасні принципи лікування серцевої недостатності зі зниженою фракцією викиду ґрунтуються на багаторівневому патофізіологічному підході, спрямованому на пригнічення надмірної активації ренін-ангіотензин-альдостеронової та симпатичної нервової систем, зменшення навантаження на міокард, уповільнення структурного ремоделювання серця та покращення прогнозу пацієнтів. Основу медикаментозної терапії становить такі препарати як інгібітори ангіотензинперетворювального ферменту або блокатори рецепторів ангіотензину II, β -адреноблокатори, антагоністи мінералокортикоїдних рецепторів та інгібітори натрій-глюкозного котранспортера 2 типу.

Keywords: cardiovascular failure, treatment, angiotensinogen, RAAS, SGLT2i, ARNI

Ключові слова: серцево-судинна недостатність, лікування, ангіотензиноген, РААС, інгібітори НЗГТК-2, ІРАН

Materials and methods: we conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Current information on the principles of treatment of heart failure with a reduced fraction was analyzed.

Purpose: to analyze scientific works, literary sources and determine the current principles of treatment of heart failure with a reduced fraction.

Relevance: Heart failure (HF) remains a global health problem that requires a multidisciplinary approach [1]. There are approximately 37.7 million cases of HF in the world and the prevalence of this condition is increasing every year [2].

HF is defined as a clinical syndrome caused by reduced cardiac output, which leads to insufficient perfu-

sion of target organ tissues or maintenance of target organ perfusion due to increased ventricular filling pressure. HF is generally classified by left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) into HF with reduced ejection fraction (LVEF < 40%), HF with midrange ejection fraction (LVEF 40% to 50%), HF with preserved ejection fraction (LVEF > 50%), and HF with restored LVEF (LVEF previously < 40% but improved to > 40% with drug therapy).

The pathophysiology of HF with reduced ejection fraction involves multiple complex mechanisms and pathways. These processes can be generally divided into neurohormonal and hemodynamic changes. Although these changes are initially activated to preserve target organ perfusion, they eventually become maladaptive, propagating the adverse structural changes that characterize HF and cause the clinical syndrome. This process is widely referred to as adverse remodeling, and its attenuation or reversal is the primary goal of most reduced ejection fraction HF therapies. Major neurohormonal adaptations to HF with reduced ejection fraction include activation of the sympathetic nervous system and the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS). Activation of the sympathetic nervous system can occur under conditions of low systemic pressure determined by arterial baroreceptors. The result is increased release and decreased reuptake of catecholamines such as norepinephrine. In the early stages, such changes maintain myocardial contractility and increase heart rate to maintain cardiac output. However, over time, the benefits of prolonged activation of the sympathetic nervous system diminish due to downregulation and desensitization of cardiac β -adrenergic receptors (especially β -1 receptors) [3]. The β -adrenergic system is mainly represented by β 1-receptors in the heart and β 2-receptors in smooth muscles. Activation of β 1-receptors by endogenous catecholamines increases the frequency and force of heart contractions, however, in HF with a reduced ejection fraction, chronic neurohormonal activation contributes to pathological remodeling of the myocardium, so β -blockers have a proven benefit [4].

Vasoconstriction caused by activation of the sympathetic nervous system increases ventricular afterload and may also cause renal vasoconstriction, which initially promotes filtration but ultimately stimulates sodium reabsorption in the proximal tubule, exacerbating volume overload. Renal release of renin stimulates the RAAS in response to decreased distensibility of glomerular afferent arterioles, decreased chloride delivery to the renal macula, and activation of the sympathetic nervous system. This leads to increased conversion of angiotensin I to angiotensin II by angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE). Angiotensin II has similar effects to norepinephrine, including induction of systemic and renal vasoconstriction and increased renal sodium reabsorption, mediated in part by increased aldosterone release. Angiotensin II also promotes myocyte hypertrophy and apoptosis, leading to myocardial interstitial fibrosis.

Natriuretic peptides are released from atrial (atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP)) and ventricular (B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP)) tissues in response to increased

intracardiac pressure. These peptides induce a variety of cardiovascular changes that generally counteract the effects of sympathetic nervous system and RAAS activation, including inhibition of myocardial vasoconstriction and collagen deposition and fibroblast activity, as well as promotion of natriuresis. Another compound known to have vasodilatory effects is nitric oxide (NO), which is partially synthesized by endothelial cells. HF with reduced ejection fraction is associated with endothelial dysfunction and resulting impairment of both NO release and sensitivity, which exacerbates chronic vasoconstriction and ventricular loading. Neurohormonal blockade achieved by simultaneous inhibition of the sympathetic nervous system and the RAAS is central to the medical treatment of HF with a reduced ejection fraction [3].

Results and Discussion: Our article focuses on a specific approach to treating only HF with reduced ejection fraction. Optimal drug therapy for HF with a reduced ejection fraction that meets the guidelines includes RAAS inhibitors, angiotensin-neprilysin receptor inhibitor (ARI), β -blockers (bisoprolol, carvedilol, or long-acting metoprolol), a mineralocorticoid antagonist (spironolactone or eplerenone), and a sodium-dependent glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor (SGLT-2) (dapagliflozin or empagliflozin) [2,5].

β -blockers

β -Blockers inhibit activation of the sympathetic nervous system and are one of the first classes to demonstrate improved outcomes in HF with reduced ejection fraction. In addition to their role in reducing myocardial ischemia and antiarrhythmic effects, long-term suppression of the sympathetic nervous system by β -blockers may increase the energy available for myocyte repair and maintenance by favoring the metabolism of glucose rather than free fatty acids as the myocyte substrate, and even inhibiting renin secretion. Selective β -1 receptor antagonists, including bisoprolol, carvedilol, and metoprolol succinate, have demonstrated improved survival and beneficial left ventricular structural changes (ie, reverse remodeling). In addition, heart rate reduction demonstrated reverse left ventricular remodeling independent of sympathetic nervous system suppression. These include improved left ventricular diastolic function and end-diastolic pressure, as well as increased endothelial cell function and proliferation, leading to improved NO availability [3].

RAAS inhibitors (ACE inhibitors/angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs))

Several classes of drugs inhibit the RAAS at various metabolic steps, including ACE inhibitors (ACE inhibitors) and angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs). ACEIs have been considered the gold standard for RAAS inhibition in HF with reduced ejection fraction for over three decades. Both reversible left ventricular remodeling and improved long-term outcomes have been demonstrated in clinical trials. ACE inhibitors prevent the reverse remodeling of angiotensin I to angiotensin II, thus limiting the latter's side effects. ACEIs also inhibit the breakdown of bradykinin, a potent vasodilator inflammatory mediator, thereby contributing to its beneficial effects and enhancing its potent afterload-reducing effects. ARBs are considered as

an alternative therapy to ACEIs, often for patients who cannot tolerate ACEIs. ARBs work by selectively blocking the angiotensin II type I receptor. Although inhibition of angiotensin II side effects is thought to be more complete with ARBs compared to ACE inhibitors due to the formation of angiotensin II unrelated to the ACE pathway, ARBs do not reduce the breakdown of bradykinin as ACE inhibitors do [3]. IRAN

ARNI is a newer class of therapy for the treatment of reduced ejection fraction HF, represented by the addition of neprilysin inhibition to angiotensin receptor (valsartan) and valsartan (angiotensin receptor II) inhibition. Neprilysin is an endopeptidase responsible for the cleavage of several endogenous vasoactive peptides that are useful in HF patients with reduced ejection fraction, including natriuretic peptides, bradykinin, adrenomedullin, and others. These effects lead to a greater hypotensive effect and additional efficacy compared to ACE inhibitors or angiotensin II receptor blockers, but also to greater intolerance, requiring therapy with ACE inhibitors or angiotensin II receptor blockers in a minority (10% to 20%) of patients [3]. ARNI demonstrated greater hemodynamic and neurohormonal effects in patients with heart failure [6].

SGLT2 (Sodium-Glucose Co-Transporter 2) inhibitors

A class of drugs that has recently demonstrated efficacy for the treatment of HF with a reduced ejection fraction is SGLT-2 inhibitors. SGLT-2 inhibitors increase urinary glucose excretion and were originally developed as oral hypoglycemic agents for the treatment of diabetes. However, they have since demonstrated beneficial effects in the treatment of HF with reduced ejection fraction in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients [3,7]. SGLT-2 treatment had a limited effect on arterial pressure and even increased arterial elasticity of HF with reduced ejection fraction. In addition, the stroke volume of the left ventricle also decreases [8].

Ivabradine

Ivabradine is another agent that takes advantage of the reduction in heart rate in patients with HF treated with reduced ejection fraction, is ivabradine, a selective sinus node inhibitor that reduces heart rate by inhibiting the I_h channel, slowing diastolic depolarization without affecting blood pressure. Ivabradine is more effective at a higher heart rate because a relatively larger proportion of I_h channels are open [3].

There is a potential advantage to starting patients on at least four drugs. However, because these drugs lower the patient's blood pressure, a pragmatic approach to the treatment plan may need to be considered. The step-by-step approach used so far often results in patients receiving maximum doses of two or possibly three drugs and poorly tolerating the addition of the third and fourth drugs [9,10].

Conclusion: Therefore, modern strategies for the treatment of HF with a reduced ejection fraction are aimed not only at reducing clinical symptoms, but also at modifying the course of the disease by suppressing key neurohormonal mechanisms responsible for the

progression of cardiac dysfunction and myocardial remodeling. The main groups of drugs used are β -blockers, RAAS inhibitors such as ACE inhibitors and ARBs, ARNI, NZKTG-2 inhibitors and ivabradine.

References:

1. Fibbi G, Sato R, Vatic M, Genreith FP, von Haehling S. Pharmacological management of heart failure: a patient-centred approach. *Expert Opin Pharmacother*. 2024 Nov;25(16):2151-2165. doi: 10.1080/14656566.2024.2418414. Epub 2024 Nov 11. PMID: 39434709.

2. Bhandari M, Pradhan A, Vishwakarma P, Singh A, Sethi R. Sodium glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors in the management of heart failure: Veni, Vidi, and Vici. *World J Cardiol*. 2024 Oct 26;16(10):550-563. doi: 10.4330/wjc.v16.i10.550. PMID: 39492976; PMCID: PMC11525799.

3. Miller RJH, Howlett JG, Fine NM. A Novel Approach to Medical Management of Heart Failure With Reduced Ejection Fraction. *Can J Cardiol*. 2021 Apr;37(4):632-643. doi: 10.1016/j.cjca.2020.12.028. Epub 2021 Jan 14. PMID: 33453357.

4. Yoon S, Eom GH. Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: present status and future directions. *Exp Mol Med*. 2019 Dec 19;51(12):1-9. doi: 10.1038/s12276-019-0323-2. PMID: 31857581; PMCID: PMC6923411.

5. Kittleson MM. Guidelines for treating heart failure. *Trends Cardiovasc Med*. 2025 Apr;35(3):141-150. doi: 10.1016/j.tcm.2024.10.002. Epub 2024 Oct 21. PMID: 39442740.

6. Yan Y, Liu B, Du J, Wang J, Jing X, Liu Y, Deng S, Du J, She Q. SGLT2i versus ARNI in heart failure with reduced ejection fraction: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *ESC Heart Fail*. 2021 Jun;8(3):2210-2219. doi: 10.1002/ehf2.13313. Epub 2021 Mar 21. PMID: 33749159; PMCID: PMC8120387.

7. Girerd N, Zannad F. SGLT2 inhibition in heart failure with reduced or preserved ejection fraction: Finding the right patients to treat. *J Intern Med*. 2023 May;293(5):550-558. doi: 10.1111/joim.13620. Epub 2023 Mar 5. PMID: 36871279.

8. van de Bovenkamp AA, Nassiri S, Bakermans AJ, Burchell GL, de Man FS, van Loon RB, Handoko ML. Long-term hemodynamic responses and reverse remodeling after pharmacotherapy in HFpEF versus HFrEF: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol*. 2025 Mar 1;328(3):H419-H432. doi: 10.1152/ajpheart.00544.2024. Epub 2025 Jan 18. PMID: 39825764.

9. Evidence review for medicines for heart failure with reduced ejection fraction: Chronic heart failure in adults: diagnosis and management: Evidence review A. London: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE); 2025 Sep. PMID: 41284794.

10. Albert NM, Young JB. Heart failure disease management: a team approach. *Cleve Clin J Med*. 2001 Jan;68(1):53-62; discussion 63-4. doi: 10.3949/ccjm.68.1.53. PMID: 11204366.